

Control of leaf blast of rice by Kasumin

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With the introduction of high yielding varieties, blast caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* has become a minor disease in Bangladesh. But under highly favorable conditions, it is often serious.

The use of resistant varieties is undoubtedly the most economical method of disease control, but chemicals must be used until susceptible varieties are replaced. A field trial of the antibiotic Kasumin was conducted at Jessore in August 1976 during the kharif season. The variety BR 2 (Mala) was sprayed with Kasumin at 1.12 kg/ha when leafblast symptoms occurred at maximum tillering stage. Three applications were made at 7-day intervals. Twenty days after the last application, 25 leaf samples were

randomly collected from a 0.83 sq-m area with and without treatment, and the percentage of leaf infection was determined.

Kasumin reduced leaf infection from 34.3% to 3.3% in the nontreated observation: 1,222 of 3,555 leaves examined were infected. In the treated samples, 130 of the 3,905 leaves examined were infected. Because of its antibiotic property, Kasumin may be preferred to other fungicides now available in Bangladesh.

Integrated control of rice pests in farmers' fields in Thailand

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An integrated program of pest control was conducted in 1976 in areas of about 0.8 – 1.92 ha in North, Northeast,

Central, and South Thailand to determine yield of various rice varieties when insecticides, fungicides, and fertilizers were applied at recommended rates. Results serve as basic information for a larger integrated control program supported by a group of farmers. Materials and methods used were the same in every region: rice seeds were treated with mancozeb (3 gm/kg seed). Carbofuran was applied at 31.25 kg/ha, and MIPC W.P. at 25 g/20 liters of water. The insecticides were applied to the

seedbeds to eliminate green leafhoppers (*Nephotettix* sp.), vectors of yellow orange leaf virus in regions where the disease causes severe damage.

Information from regional plots is summarized (see table). Results for the regions follow:

1. North: RD9, a nonglutinous variety, was moderately resistant (3.6% damage) to the gall midge *Puchydiplosis oryzae*. Local glutinous varieties LL and NSPT had 14.5% and 35.1% damage, respectively. Although RD9 is fertilizer

Some results from plots for integrated control of rice pests in Thailand, 1976.

Variety	Pest damage (%) ^a		Cost (US\$/ha)			Yield (t/ha)	Income (US\$/ha)	Net income (US\$/ha)
	BLB disease	Insects	Chemical	Fertilizer	Cultural and labor			
<i>North: Chiangrai</i>								
RD9*	17	GM 3.6	43.75	35.63	144	3.7	461	238
Lai Luang	30	GM 14.5	43.75	35.63	144	2.9	367	144
Lai Luang	30	GM 20.0	0.00	0.00	144	2.8	352	208
Niaw San Pahtawng*	30	GM 35.1	43.15	35.63	144	2.2	281	58
<i>Northeast: Khon Khan</i>								
RD5*	1	0	0.67	21.81	105	7.4	688	561
RD7*	1	0	0.67	21.81	105	6.9	642	514
Khi-Tom-Yai	15	0	5.80	21.81	105	4.5	307	174
Khi-Tom-Yai	30	SB 0.5	0.67	0.00	105	3.6	241	135
<i>Central: Chacheongsao</i>								
RD7*	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	2.3	289	102
RD9*	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	3.2	398	212
Khao Khao	0.5	0	5.69	23.75	157	2.9	363	176
<i>South: Phatalung</i>								
BKN 6402-352	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.9	294	99
NPY132*	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	3.6	263	68
PN43*	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.1	209	14
Lon Krok	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	2.1	211	16
Khai Mod Rin	5	SB 7-10	25.94	16.72	152	1.8	178	- 17

^a BLB = bacterial leaf blight; GM = gall midge; SB = stem borer, * = government-recommended variety.